

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF CAREER CHOICE IN SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. This article explores the psychological characteristics of the career choice process among students. The interrelation between career choice, personal development, academic motivation, and social factors is analyzed. The study involved 120 students aged 16–18 and applied several psychological methods to assess their levels of career inclination and academic motivation. The results indicated that students with a high level of career inclination also demonstrated high academic motivation. The author emphasizes the necessity of guiding students toward suitable careers through psychological diagnostics and counseling services and highlights the critical role of school psychologists and parents in this process.

Keywords: career choice, psychological characteristics, career inclination, academic motivation, students, career guidance, psychological support, personal development, methodology, diagnostics.

In modern society, the process of career choice plays an important role not only in individual development but also in the economic and social progress of a country. For school students, career choice is a fundamental stage that determines their life trajectory, making it essential to study the psychological aspects of this process in depth.

As emphasized by President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev: “Yoshlarimizning kasb-hunar egallashi, ularning intellektual salohiyatini to’g’ri yo’naltirish – bu davlatimizning eng ustuvor vazifalaridan biridir” [1.1-p.]. In the New Uzbekistan, equipping young learners with vocational skills remains one of the most pressing tasks of today. Indeed, a profession chosen based on one’s abilities, interests, motivations, and goals contributes not only to the formation of a well-rounded individual but also to the development of a competent specialist who serves society and actively contributes to its progress, ultimately enabling the individual to grow into a happy and independent person.

In developed countries such as Germany, Japan, and the United States, specialized programs, psychological tests, and counseling services have been established to determine students’ career orientation. These practices help students choose professions that correspond to their abilities and interests.

Literature Review. Uzbek scholars have also been extensively studying the psychological aspects of career choice. In particular, the scientific works conducted under the guidance of researchers such as E.G. Goziyev, B.R. Qodirov, B.M. Umarov, B. Shoumarov, V.M. Karimova, Z.T. Nishonova, Z. Abdurahmonova, F.A. Akramova, R.I. Sunnatova, N.S. Safoyev, D. Axmedova, N.X. Xolyigitova, and N. Bekmurodova provide a comprehensive analysis of attitudes as a socio-psychological category.

The analysis of the reviewed scientific literature indicates that various researchers have devoted considerable attention to studying the mechanisms of students’ career choice processes, particularly through identifying characteristics such as their professional abilities,

inclinations, and interests. Nevertheless, this phenomenon is distinguished by its complex and multifaceted nature and is interpreted from different perspectives. This suggests that issues related to career choice and career guidance are not new to the modern era; rather, they have long been at the center of scientific inquiry as a relevant and enduring problem.

Research Methods. The study was conducted in a general secondary education school in Uzbekistan with the participation of 120 students aged 16–18. The following methodologies were employed in the research.

G.V. Rezapkina's "Questionnaire for Determining Professional Inclinations" served as an important tool for identifying students' career interests [2.2–3-p.]. Holland's "Vocational Types Identification" methodology was used to determine types of professions corresponding to students' personal characteristics [3.6-p.]. A.D. Ishkov's "Diagnostics of Self-Organization Characteristics", Gerbachevskiy's "Level of Aspiration" test, and the "Academic Motivation Scale" developed by T.O. Gordeyeva, O.A. Sechev, and E.N. Osin were also applied [4.27-p.]. In addition, a "Psychological Questionnaire for Identifying Career Choice" (author's methodology) was utilized.

Results and Discussion. The findings of the study indicate that the levels of students' professional inclinations were identified across high, medium, and low scales (Table 1). Among the 120 respondents, high-level indicators were observed in 45 students (37.5%). Medium-level indicators were identified in 50 students (41.7%), while low-level indicators were found in 25 students (20.8%).

Table 1. Levels of Students' Professional Inclinations

Kasbiy moyillik darajasi	O'quvchilar soni	Foiz (%)
Yuqori	45	37.5
O'rta	50	41.7
Past	25	20.8

Furthermore, the study also examined the levels of students' academic motivation (high, medium, and low). The results showed that a high level of academic motivation was observed in 48 students (40%), a medium level in 52 students (43.3%), and a low level in 20 students (16.7%).

Table 2. Levels of Academic Motivation

Motivatsiya darajasi	O'quvchilar soni	Foiz (%)
Yuqori	48	40.0
O'rta	52	43.3
Past	20	16.7

Diagram 1. Comparison of the Levels of Professional Inclination and Academic Motivation

Diagram Analysis. As can be seen from the diagram, students with a high level of professional inclination also demonstrate a high level of academic motivation. In particular, 37.5% of students had a high level of professional inclination, and within this group, 40% also showed a high level of academic motivation. The proportion of students with a medium level of professional inclination (41.7%) is almost consistent with the proportion of students with a medium level of academic motivation (43.3%). Similarly, a low level of professional inclination (20.8%) corresponds to a low level of academic motivation (16.7%). These figures indicate that the clarity of career orientation may have a strong influence on students' enthusiasm for learning activities. Therefore, guiding students toward suitable career paths can contribute to increasing their overall academic motivation.

As the diagram further illustrates, there is a close interrelationship between students' professional inclination levels and academic motivation. Students with a high level of professional inclination also tend to have a high level of academic motivation.

Discussion. As an example of the social determinants in the formation of career choice, we identified the following factors.

Family and environment. "Kasbiy tanlovni shakllantirishda ijtimoiy determinantlariga misol qilib ushbularni keltirdik. Oila va atrof-muhit Ota-onalar, aka-uka yoki opa-singillar, va boshqa yaqinlar o'quvchilarning kasbiy tanlovlariga katta ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Ota-onalar ko'pincha o'z kasbiy tajribalari va qadriyatlarini orqali bolalarining tanloviiga yo'nalish beradilar"[4.28-p.]. The profession, aspirations, and encouragement of parents can serve as examples of social influence in shaping a child's career choice.

The results of the study indicate that career choice among students is associated with motivational, personal, and social factors. Students with a high level of professional inclination tend to be more clearly goal-oriented and more inclined to make independent decisions. Academic motivation also emerged as an important factor influencing career choice. Students with a defined career orientation are more active in self-awareness, assessing their abilities, and identifying life goals. This, in turn, highlights once again the importance of psychological support services within the education system.

Conclusion and Recommendations. Career choice is one of the key processes in the formation of a student's personality. Through psychological diagnostics and counseling

services, it is possible to guide students toward professions that correspond to their abilities. Therefore, we propose the following recommendations:

- To organize training courses for school psychologists on methodologies for identifying career preferences.
- To establish career guidance centers in every general secondary education institution.
- To involve parents in actively participating in the development of their children's abilities and in the career choice process.

In this process, the support of parents and society is also of great importance. As stated: "...o'qituvchilar va psixologlar o'quvchilarning shaxsiy xususiyatlarini aniqlab, ularga individual maslahat va amaliy mashg'ulotlar orqali kasb tanlashda yo'l-yo'riq ko'rsatishlari kerak." [5.417-p.].

Such measures enable students to make informed decisions in the career selection process, to understand their strengths and weaknesses, to choose professions that meet labor market demands, and to achieve success in their future professional activities. Furthermore, this systematic approach develops students' sense of responsibility, initiative, and independent decision-making skills. The availability of psychological support in career choice facilitates students' socio-psychological adaptation, reduces stress levels, and increases self-confidence. As a result, society benefits from individuals who are satisfied with their profession, motivated, and capable of effective performance.

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